

Mental nourishment in a world full of distractions

Amazon Readers

January 8, 2025

Following are new reviews from Amazon readers, which were posted during the new year holiday.

B. Willy (A Thoughtful Feast for the Mind, January 3, 2025)

This book serves a delightful mix of wit, philosophy, and science, offering brief yet profound reflections on thinking and life. With innovative insights and moments of humor, it's a perfect read for those seeking clarity and calm in a noisy world. [1]

The W Fam (Loved it, January 3, 2025)

This is a really good book. I couldn't put it down. I would absolutely read more by this author! [2]

Scott M. Fraley (Insightful, January 2, 2025)

This book includes entertaining stories that provide valuable life insights. Good read! [3]

Gordon C (Good One!, January 1, 2025)

I appreciate how the content, though brief, offers more than surface-level observations—it's a meditation on life, thought, and tranquility in a fast-paced world. The comparisons to nature and the reflection on human cognition really resonated with me. A perfect read for those who crave mental nourishment in a world full of distractions. [4]

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Helpful

Report

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(*) Note: This post reprints reviewers' comment on the Amazon page of Meandering Sobriety [1].

Tom Terrific (Meandering Sobriety, December 30, 2024)

Quan-Hoang Vuong's book, Meandering Sobriety is a collection of seemingly random thoughts/stories/real world applications that are thought provoking, entertaining and even funny. Don't get me wrong, the content is quite intellectual and reveals the genius behind the prose. This is a book made to get your brain cells fired up without the usual thrills provided in the average book today. Recommended for the thinkers out there. Good work Quan-Hoang.

Stacy Gagnani (Sobering Thoughts from a Brain-Buffer, December 29, 2024)

What a weird and wonderful little book! It's like sitting down for coffee with a super smart friend who jumps from ancient riddles to science theories while somehow making it all make sense. The author's stories about finding peace in our crazy social media world really hit home, and his mix of humor and deep thinking keeps you hooked. Perfect for anyone who wants brain food.

References

[1] Willy, B. (2025). A Thoughtful Feast for the Mind. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2QZ038734WNVN/>

[2] Fam, T. W. (2025). Loved it. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R3F4Y9CF7W6LFF/>

[3] Fraley, S. M. (2025). Insightful. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RWXG59MVJXCGZ/>

- [4] Gordon, C. (2025). Good One!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RNBFCX42GOW41/>
- [5] Terrific, T. (2024). Meandering Sobriety. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RIS37T5DMLH16/>
- [6] Gagnani, S. (2024). Sobering Thoughts from a Brain-Buffer. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2WPBWT09QJDU7/>
- [7] Vuong, Q. H. (2023). Meandering Sobriety. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0C2TXNX6L>